

Electron Positron Decay and the Higgs – 8T

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Abstract:

Following the previous paper regarding $\gamma\gamma^-$ interaction yielding a higgs boson, one would like to suggest another decay, pairing an electron positron pair to yield a Higgs boson. Analysis will be done via the coupling constants primorial equation. In contrast to previous paper, there will not be an analysis of the net variation, but only the destabilizing factor, i.e. the electron, manifested in the invariant (3) in each coupling term from the second and above.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

If there is an elimination of the destabilizer, i.e. the majestic (3) there will be no propagation of the boson from the fermion and the result would be again spin zero. In the 8T thesis, we constructed four categories for particle classifications using the primorial coupling constants equation:

Spin zero: ($2N$ variations)

Matter with spin one-half: ($2N$ variations + 3)

Bosons with spin one: ($2N$ variations + 3) + N_V

Bosons with higher spin integers: ($2N$ variations + 3) + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + $\dots \rightarrow$

According to the following framework, the pairing of electron positron pair than can also construct an emerging of the Higgs. Since the Higgs has only one term in the coupling series, prediction would be propagation similar to gravity, that is local and short ranged.

$$ee^+ \rightarrow H^0$$

$$ee^+ \rightarrow 4N$$

We can expand that result and say that any amount of even inverse in sign, fermions of the kind of majestic (3), i.e. the electron and its anti-matter dual, pairing to each other will yield a spin zero particle of certain sort. This particle again can be morphed into a new distinct particle given:

$$2N + 2N = 2 \sum_{i=1}^K N_i$$

If we eliminate the destabilizer there is no need to analyze the photons pairing. As one is a mathematical physicist and not a particle physicist, the reaction suggested may have been known already for a long time. However his prediction is made according to a new theory which predicts the magnitude of coupling constants, and so may shed new light on the interactions among particles and unveil at least some of the complexity in that wonderful area of research.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)